

Structural snapshots of 26S proteasome in the presence of tetraubiquitin reveal novel conformations

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Summary

The 26S proteasome is the ATP-dependent protease responsible for regulating the proteome of eukaryotic cells through degradation of mainly ubiquitin-tagged substrates. In order to understand how proteasome responds to ubiquitin signal, we resolved an ensemble of cryo-EM structures of proteasome in the presence of K48-Ub₄, with three of them resolved at near-atomic resolution. We identified a new conformation with stabilized ubiquitin receptors and a previously unreported orientation of the lid, assigned as a Ub-accepted state C1-b. We determined another structure C3-b with localized K48-Ub₄ to the toroid region of Rpn1, assigned as a substrate-processing state. Our structures indicate tetraUb induced conformational changes in proteasome could initiate substrate degradation. We also propose a CP gate-opening mechanism involving the propagation of the motion of the lid to the gate through the Rpn6- α 2 interaction. Our results enabled us to put forward a model of a functional cycle for proteasomes induced by tetraUb.

Introduction

Ubiquitin (Ub) is an evolutionarily conserved protein consisting of 76 residues and serves as a signal in a myriad of essential biological processes. The Ub-proteasome system (UPS) is the ATP-dependent pathway for degradation of misfolded, abnormal, and short-lived proteins in eukaryotic cells (Finley, 2009; Schwartz and Ciechanover, 2009). Dysfunction of the UPS is often found in cancers (Petroski, 2008) and neurodegenerative diseases (Schmidt and Finley, 2014). Ub conjugated by isopeptide bonds to lysine residues on substrate molecules and on other Ub molecules leads to the formation of polymeric Ub chains on substrate. The best understood type of polyUb chain is linked through lysine 48 (K48) of each Ub unit. Such K48-linked polyUb chains with the length of four or more, serve as the predominant proteasome-targeting signal (Mansour et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2016; Thrower et al., 2000). After association of the polyUb conjugate, the 26S proteasome translocates and unfolds the substrate, followed by deubiquitination and irreversible degradation (Demartino and Gillette, 2007; Groll et al., 2005; Smith et al., 2006; Voges et al., 1999).

The 26S proteasome is a dynamic ATP-dependent macromolecular machine, comprising a 20S core particle (CP) capped by one or two 19S regulatory particles (RPs) (Asano et al., 2015; Budenholzer et al., 2017). The CP is a hollow cylinder of four stacked rings: two β rings at the center and two α rings on each end. Exposure of substrate to the proteolytic active sites of the β subunits is strictly controlled by α rings (Yu and Matouschek, 2017). Substrates enter the CP through a gated channel within the α ring that is so narrow (~ 13 Å) that only unfolded peptides can pass (Groll et al., 2000). The RP, further dissected into a base and a lid, is responsible for recognition of ubiquinated substrate, deubiquitination, unfolding, and translocation. The base positioned on the α ring contains an AAA-ATPase heterohexamers formed by Rpt1-6, two large subunits (Rpn1 and Rpn2), and Rpn13. The lid situated asymmetrically on one side of the base, comprises non-ATPase regulatory subunits Rpn3, Rpn5-9, Rpn11, Rpn12, and Sem1 (Lander et al., 2012; Matyskiela et al., 2013;

Unverdorben et al., 2014). Opening of the CP gate in the 26S holoenzyme is regulated by the C-termini of ATPase subunit (Kohler et al., 2001; Rabl et al., 2008; Smith et al., 2007). Most available structures of the 26S proteasome are in the closed-gate conformation except for s4 (yeast) (Eisele et al., 2018; Wehmer et al., 2017) and S_D (human) (Chen et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2018) in the open conformation, and s2 and s3 in the partially open conformation (Wehmer et al., 2017).

Three integral proteasome subunits (Rpn1, Rpn10 and Rpn13) have been reported to bind polyUb (Deveraux et al., 1994; Husnjak et al., 2008; Shi et al., 2016), although their individual contribution to the overall affinity of proteasomes for polyUb remains unclear. Moreover, these subunits also serve as receptors for transient association of shuttles (Rad23, Dsk2, and Ddi1) that mediate binding of polyUb chains, pointing to parallel modes of targeting ubiquitinated substrates to proteasomes (Chojnacki et al., 2017; Matiuhin et al., 2008; Rosenzweig et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2009). The largest of the three receptors, Rpn1, includes a centrally located domain composed of 11 proteasome/cyclosome (PC) repeats of helix-turn-helix hairpins which curve into a closed toroid (Effantin et al., 2009; He et al., 2012; Kajava, 2002). This toroid can serve as a multipurpose scaffold since it can bind Ub or Ub-binding proteins such as Rad23 and Ubp6 (Budenholzer et al., 2017). Recently, the Ub binding region on Rpn1 was narrowed down to the first PC repeat cluster (Chojnacki et al., 2017; Shi et al., 2016). Another Ub-receptor, Rpn10, is positioned at the periphery of the lid, and Rpn13 is the most distal component of the 26S assembly.

With advanced cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM), continual efforts over the course of several decades resolved multiple conformational states and functional intermediates of the proteasome in the presence of nucleotides, nucleotide analogs (Beck et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2016; da Fonseca et al., 2012; Ding et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2016; Lander et al., 2012; Luan et al., 2016; Schweitzer et al., 2016; Unverdorben et al., 2014; Wehmer et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2018) and substrate (de la Pena et al., 2018; Dong et al., 2018; Matyskiela et al., 2013). In the presence of ATP, proteasomes are prone to stay in a putative resting state, characterized by mismatched

N-ring, AAA-ring, and the entrance of the CP. In contrast, its activated state is featured by coaxial alignment of the substrate translocation channel, rotation of the lid upon the base, and a rotary movement of the intrinsic deubiquitylase Rpn11 to a position enabling deubiquitylation of the substrate as it transverses through the channel. According to the structural details, several functional states had been defined, resting state (s1), substrate commitment (s2), translocation (s3), and degradation (s4) states (Unverdorben et al., 2014; Wehmer et al., 2017).

Structural information of K48-Ub₄ bound to proteasome is an essential piece of information to understand how proteasomes respond to a proper degradation signal. The present study describes the mode of interaction between K48 linked tetraUb (K48-Ub₄) and the proteasome, as well as conformational changes potentially induced by K48-Ub₄. We obtained an ensemble of yeast proteasome cryo-EM structures in different functional states with some of them resolved at near atomic resolution. We identified a new conformation of proteasome in which K48-Ub₄ was localized to the toroid surface of Rpn1, substantiated by our biochemical analysis, compatible for simultaneous binding of K48-Ub₄, Ubp6, and Rad23. Our results also reveal how the presence of tetraUb transduces allosteric changes of proteasome conformation from lid through base to CP gate-opening.

Results

Conformational States of the 26S Proteasome in the Presence of K48-Ub₄

We carried out cryo-EM analysis of yeast 26S proteasome in the presence of K48-Ub₄ and ATP, and identified five distinct conformational species (Figure 1 and Table S1). Our small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) data revealed a discrepancy in the large-radius region of the P(r) profile among the K48-Ub₄, ATP, and ADP-AlFx states of proteasome (Figure S1A), implying a proteasome conformational change induced by K48-Ub₄. The proteasome particles were firstly categorized into two states: resting state (69.3%) and activated state (30.7%) (Figure S2), as judged by the alignment status of the substrate translocation channel. This relative ratio between

resting and activated states in the proteasome conformational landscape is consistent with our previous result on proteasome with ATP alone system (Ding et al., 2017), and the overall trend is comparable with available reports on yeast proteasome with other nucleotide analogs (Wehmer et al., 2017) (Figure S4A).

Based on the dataset of the resting-state proteasome, we resolved a map at 3.5 Å resolution and assigned it as C1 (Figure S1D, S1F, and S1H), which overall resembles the available resting-state conformation (Ding et al., 2017; Luan et al., 2016; Wehmer et al., 2017). Further 3D classification of this dataset allowed us to obtain two distinct subpopulations both in the resting-state, namely C1-a and C1-b (Figures 1A-B and S2). We then refined both maps to a nominal resolution of 3.8 Å, with the local resolution varying from 2.9 Å to 5.5 Å (Figure S1G and S1I-J), and built a pseudo-atomic model for each of the maps (Figure S3). Overlaying our C1-a model on that of the available s1 resting state (Wehmer et al., 2017) revealed they adopt similar conformations with misaligned substrate translocation channel (Figure S4B), suggesting that C1-a is also in a resting state without bound Ub. We therefore used this Ub-free C1-a map as the resting state for subsequent structural analysis. However, C1-b was found to differ from C1-a, especially in the upper part of RP (including Rpn2, Rpn3, Rpn9, Rpn10, and Rpn12), which tilted “downward” toward Rpn1 (Movie 1), not reported before. This motion may initiate the transition from resting to activated state, shifting the conformational equilibrium away from the resting state. Additionally, although these two maps were determined to similar nominal resolutions, C1-b map reveals better structural details in Rpn1 and the upper part of the RP (Figure S1I-J), implying the intrinsic dynamic movements in these regions in C1-a are more stabilized in C1-b.

We classified and refined the activated proteasome dataset into two distinct conformational states, designated as C2 and C3, at resolution of 4.5 Å and 6.8 Å, respectively (Figures 1C, S1E-F, S1K, and S2). We then performed further 3D classification on each dataset independently. This analysis retained the C2 dataset as a single conformation. But for the C3 dataset, we resolved two compositionally distinct

states, C3-a and C3-b, at 7.0 Å and 7.5 Å resolution, respectively (Figures 1D-E, S1G and S2). Comparing with the available yeast proteasome structures in the activated states (s2~s4 states) (Wehmer et al., 2017), C2 shows an overall similar conformation to s2, both have Rpn11 moved towards the center of the substrate translocation channel, but Rpn10 in C2 exhibits an extra downward tilt motion toward CP (Figure S4D). C3-a and s3 are in a similar conformation with fully aligned substrate translocation channel, but the ATPase ring and Rpn10 of C3-a show a rearrangement compared with s3 (Figure S4E). Noteworthy, the overall conformation of C3-b is similar to s4, yet C3-b has an obvious extra density residing in a distinct location from that of the Ubp6 in s4 (Figures S4F-G, 3A, and S5D). These considerable conformational changes in our structures emerge from comparison, indicate the influence of K48-Ub₄.

Additionally, we reconstructed a 3.3-Å-resolution cryo-EM map of free 20S proteasome existing in our dataset (Figure S1L).

Structural Features of the Proteasome Related to K48-Ub₄-Binding

To measure the differences in conformational mobility between C1-a and C1-b, we calculated the B-factors of these models (Haselbach et al., 2017). In C1-a, the B-factors of Rpn10, Rpn2, and Rpn1 were calculated to be higher than those of the other subunits, indicating a rather dynamic nature for these three subunits (Figure 2A). As mentioned, Rpn10 and Rpn1 are Ub receptors, and Rpn2 connects to another Ub receptor Rpn13. Therefore, the intrinsic dynamic nature of these subunits may facilitate the recruitment of polyUb or Ub-conjugated proteins. In contrast, in C1-b, Rpn10, Rpn2, and Rpn1 showed obviously lower B-factor values than they did in C1-a, and the entire lid was stabilized to some extent (Figure 2A). Considering the relatively stabilized Ub-binding related subunits in this newly resolved C1-b state that in a distinct conformation compared with the available structures, and the presence of K48-Ub₄ in the proteasome sample, C1-b may represent a Ub-induced proteasome conformation, while remaining in the resting state. Moreover, C1-b was reconstructed

from the largest population (42.7%) of the dataset (Figure S2). These data suggest that C1-b may represent the dominant configuration of the Ub₄-induced proteasome.

Conformational comparison between C1-a and C1-b, by overlaying their pseudo atomic models, suggests that the conformational transition from C1-a to C1-b involves a considerable movement of Rpn2, specifically a 2.9° rotation and a 4.4 Å shift of this subunit towards Rpn1. Correlated with this movement, other subunits lying on the periphery of RP (Rpn11, Rpn9, and especially Rpn10) reposition closer to Rpn2 (Figure 2B). Collectively, in the presence of K48-Ub₄, a significant portion of proteasome population could converge into a “closed-jaw conformation” to facilitate substrate engagement.

The most notable structural feature in our activated-state maps was the extra density attached to Rpn1 in C3-b (Figure 3A). Association of K48-Ub₄ with both single- and double-capped proteasome was validated by retarded migration of proteasomes in native gel electrophoresis, whereas monoUb failed to do so even at a 4-fold molecular excess over tetraUb (Figures 3B and S5A). TetraUb was also detected by Mass Spectrometry (MS) of the retarded proteasome band (Table S2-S4). This indicates that 26S proteasomes recognize tetraUb as a fundamentally different signal from monoUb. Importantly, during the timeframe of our cryo-EM experiment (5 min), most likely K48-Ub₄ chains were only negligibly processed by proteasome and hence retained their integrity (Figure S5B), supporting our earlier report that free unanchored K48-Ub₄ chains are disassembled relatively slowly by yeast 26S proteasomes (Mansour et al., 2015). Subsequent focused refinement improved the connectivity of the map in the region of Rpn1 and the connected extra density (Figure S5C). The extra density forms a bean-like shape that appeared to be able to accommodate the blurred map of a K48-Ub₄ (PDB: 2O6V), with the cross-correlation score to be 0.76 (Figure 3C). The position of this extra density identified on Rpn1 in C3-b is distinct from that of the Ubp6 in s4 state (Wehmer et al., 2017). When docking the Rpn1-Ubp6 model from s4 state (PDB: 5MPC) into our C3-b map, Ubp6 extended beyond the extra density with the cross-correlation score only to be 0.18

(Figure S5D). This result strongly suggests that the extra density in C3-b does not correspond to Ubp6. To further confirm this novel extra density observed in our C3-b map is derived from K48-Ub₄, we performed negative staining EM (NS-EM) on the nanogold-labeled K48-Ub₄-bound proteasome system. The reference-free 2D class average reveals a dark density (attributed to the nanogold label) located in the entrance of the RP mouth near Rpn1 (Figure 3D), in a location similar to that of the extra density in C3-b assigned to tetraUb (Figure 3A). Taken together, both our cryo-EM and nanogold labeling NS-EM results localize tetraUb in a similar location near Rpn1. Still, there remains some additional density uncovered by one K48-Ub₄ (Figure 3C), which may be resulted from various conformations and orientations of K48-Ub₄ when bound to Rpn1 or correlated to UBL proteins such as Rad23. Moreover, our gel-shift assays showed that K48-Ub₄ associates with proteasomes regardless of the presence of USP14/Ubp6 (Figure S5E), indicating that Ubp6 and K48-Ub₄ are sterically compatible on Rpn1. A supershift upon addition of Rad23 indicates proteasome can accommodate Rad23, Ubp6, and K48-Ub₄ simultaneously (Figure S5E).

UBL-domains (of Rad23, Dsk2, Ubp6) and Ub (mono, di) have been shown to bind to different helical repeats of the Rpn1 PC toroid (Chojnacki et al., 2017; Shi et al., 2016). However, in our C3-b map, the putative tetraUb density is localized to a new location on the Rpn1 PC crown (Figure 3C). To determine the minimal segment of Rpn1 that can accommodate K48-Ub₄, we added recombinants to the pre-incubated 26S proteasome with K48-Ub₄, including Rpn1 PC domain, the PC-I segment that is sufficient for binding mono/di Ub, or the UIM motif of Rpn10 (Figure 3E-F). Our biochemical analyses showed that the Rpn1 PC domain alone was competent to completely strip tetraUb from proteasome (Figure 3F). Interestingly, Rpn1^{PC-I} and Rpn10^{UIM}, which are effective in binding mono or diUb, were less efficient at out-competing tetraUb prebound to 26S proteasome (Figure 3F). In contrast, Rpn10^{UIM}, Rpn1^{PC-I}, and Rpn1^{PC} were all effective in stripping Rad23^{Ubl} from proteasome (Figure S5F). These results suggest that the mode of K48-Ub₄ binding on

proteasome differs from that of its single Ub units or UBL-domains. The requirement of the full PC toroid to bind K48-Ub₄ supports our localization of K48-Ub₄ on the Rpn1 PC-crown within 26S proteasome.

Conformational Changes of the Lid upon RP Activation

The lid of the 26S proteasome is essential for the processing of polyUb-conjugates (Glickman et al., 1998), which could coordinate substrate deubiquitylation with substrate unfolding and translocation by the base (Budenholzer et al., 2017). Aligning the five maps resolved in the current study according to their shared CPs, revealed that their lids adopt considerably different conformations (Figure 4A). Specifically, the alignments revealed the occurrence of a downward motion of the upper part of RP toward Rpn1 in the transition from C1-a to C1-b (Movie 1), suggesting a rearrangement in these regions to accommodate tetraUb binding and activation of RP. A subsequent clockwise rotation of the lid by 26.3° along CP in the transition from C1-b to C2 was generated, with Rpn6 serving as a rotation anchor to maintain the interaction with α 2 subunit in the CP (Figure 4A and Movie 2), which turns the entire complex into an activated state. Following that, a counterclockwise rotation of the lid by 9.7° along CP in the transition from C2 to C3-a may further fully align the translocation channel. Finally, no significant movement of the lid in the transition from C3-a to C3-b was observed (Figure 4A), implying both C3-a and C3-b states may correspond to those in which substrates are translocating along the ATPase ring into the CP chamber.

Along with the lid rotation, the distance between Rpn5 and Rpn6 was observed to change dramatically. The distance between residue M1 of the N-terminal α -helix of Rpn6 and L27 of the N-terminal α -helix of Rpn5 was measured to be about 39.9 Å in the model of C1-a, and it was slightly reduced to 38.3 Å in C1-b — but much greater (86.6 Å) in C2, and even greater, 91.7 Å and 96.1 Å, in C3-a and C3-b, respectively (Figure 4B). The large difference in the distance between C1-b and C2 was related to the considerably different rotational orientations of the lid encompassing Rpn5, together with Rpn6 remaining bound to α 2 in both states and appearing to serve as the

anchor point for the implied rotation of the lid.

Conformational Changes of the ATPase Ring

The ATPase ring in the base serves as the motor for the ATP-driven conformational cycling of the proteasome and plays a crucial role in the substrate unfolding and translocation (Sauer and Baker, 2011). Comparison of the ATPase rings revealed apparent conformational differences in the ATPase subunits (Figure S6). While the ATPase ring is nearly identical between C1-a and C1-b (Figure S6A), the entire ATPase ring shifted ~ 10 Å towards Rpn1 in C2 relative to C1-b, but otherwise appeared to adopt quite similar conformations in C1-b and C2 (Figure S6B). This observation suggested no ATP hydrolysis to be involved during the transition from C1-b to C2, and hence the coaxial alignment of the substrate translocation channel in C2 to be correlated with the rotational motion of the lid (Figure 4A). Thus, we propose that the binding of Ub-conjugate could trigger the observed conformational changes of the lid, i.e., push the ATPase to be closer to Rpn1, and convert the complex from resting to an activated state. Comparison of the C2 and C3-a models showed an $\sim 6^\circ$ anti-clockwise rotation of the ATPase around the corner where Rpt1 and Rpt2 meet, and showed local conformational differences in the AAA domains (Figure S6C), suggesting ATP hydrolysis proceeding during the transition from C2 to C3-a. Finally, comparison of the C3-a and C3-b models showed no obvious local conformational changes but did suggest the occurrence of an $\sim 2^\circ$ clockwise rotation of the ATPase around the corner where Rpt1 and Rpt2 meet (Figure S6D).

The central pore of the ATPase ring is formed by the so-called “pore loops” protruding from each Rpt subunit, and these loops have been shown to be essential in substrate unfolding and translocation (Wang et al., 2001; Yamada-Inagawa et al., 2003). In both C1-a and C1-b maps, the pore loops were observed to show a configuration of Rpt3 at the top and Rpt2 in the bottom (Figures 5A and S7A), in line with the previous resting state configuration (Ding et al., 2017; Wehmer et al., 2017). Moreover, the relative locations of the pore loops in C2 were observed to be nearly

identical to that in the resting state (Figure S7B), further substantiating the notion that the activation of RP is triggered by the binding of Ub-conjugate instead of being driven by ATP hydrolysis. Taken together, our analysis indicated C2 to be an intermediate state just after the resting state, and that binding of K48-Ub₄ could initiate a change in the conformation of the lid, which could be subsequently propagated to the base to perform substrate processing.

Inspection of C3-a revealed a distinct pattern of the heights of the pore loops that allowed for a further classification of the Rpt subunits into three groups: Rpt5 and Rpt1 for which the pore loops were found to be highest, Rpt2 and Rpt6 with their intermediate level loops, and Rpt3 and Rpt4 for which the pore loops were lowest (Figure 5B). Moreover, the pattern of the pore loops in C3-b was found to be similar to that of s3, with those of Rpt1, Rpt4, and Rpt5 at the top, bottom, and middle, respectively (Wehmer et al., 2017) (Figure 5C). Our observations indicated a rearrangement of the ATPase and repositioning of the pore loops upon conversion from C2 to C3-a and then to C3-b and hence provided additional evidences for a progression of ATP hydrolysis to facilitate substrate unfolding and translocation.

Gate Configurations in Different States of Proteasome

Unfolded polypeptides need to pass through the narrow channel of the proteasome to reach the CP proteolytic site for the final degradation. Isolated eukaryotic 20S proteasome usually shows a closed-gate configuration (Huber et al., 2012), a feature also observed in our free 20S proteasome cryo-EM map (Figure S8A). Our C1-a and C1-b maps showed nearly identical CP features, resembling that of the combined C1 map at higher resolution (3.5 Å). Similarly, the CP features of the C3 map at higher resolution (6.8 Å) closely resemble those of C3-a and C3-b. We then inspected the gate configuration by analyzing the C1, C2, and C3 maps. In C1, the N-termini of the seven distinct α -subunits were well resolved and showed a tightly closed gate (Figures 6A and S8B). While in C2, the originally closely packed N-termini of α_2 , α_3 , and α_4 subunits became partially disordered with discontinuous

pieces of density indicating a partially open gate in C2 (Figures 6B and S8B), comparable to the structures in s2 and s3 (Wehmer et al., 2017). In C3, the termini of $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$, and $\alpha 4$ were not observed at all in the gate region, leading to a fully open CP gate (Figures 6C and S8B). These termini were assumed to have relocated toward the RP (Wehmer et al., 2017), with a configuration similar to that of the rather stable conformations of the $\alpha 1$, $\alpha 6$, and $\alpha 7$ termini. In the current study, about 22% of the particles adopted the partially open conformation (C2 state), and 8% the completely open conformation (C3 state, Figure S2).

Gate-opening Mechanism

To decipher the gate-opening mechanism, we first analyzed the structures of Rpt C-terminal tails in C1, C2, and C3 maps, since these tails play an important role in the CP gate opening (Rabl et al., 2008; Smith et al., 2007). We observed the C-terminal HbYX (hydrophobic-tyrosine-any residue) motifs of Rpt2, Rpt3, and Rpt5 were all inserted into the corresponding pockets of the CP α -ring in these maps, consistent with previous reports (Ding et al., 2017; Wehmer et al., 2017) (Figure 6A-C). Additionally, in C1 and C2, the C-termini of Rpt1 and Rpt4 were observed to run parallel to the α ring (Figure S9), while density corresponding to that of Rpt6 was not observed, in line with previous observations of the human proteasome (Huang et al., 2016). In contrast, in C3, the C-termini of Rpt1 and Rpt4 were not observed, while that of Rpt6 was determined to be inserted into the $\alpha 2$ - $\alpha 3$ pocket (Figure 6C), in agreement with previous observations in yeast proteasome s4 state at similar resolution (Wehmer et al., 2017).

The very similar C-termini configurations combined with different gate statuses displayed by the C1 and C2 maps, inspired us to explore the gate-opening mechanism. We posited the dramatic change in the lid induced by K48-Ub₄ pushed the ATPase ring (Figure 4A and S6B) and propagated allosterically to CP through the interaction between Rpn6 and $\alpha 2$ (Figure 4A). To validate this speculation, we compared the CP conformation in C1 with that in C2. This comparison revealed a conformational difference in the cis- α ring adjacent to the base (Figure 6D), but also showed the

lower three rings to match each other very well (Figure S8C). Of the seven α subunits, the gate keepers, i.e., $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$ and $\alpha 4$, showed the largest outward shift away from the central pore (2.0 to 2.8 Å for these three subunits) from C1 to C2 (Figure 6D), which may break the original interaction network stabilizing the closed-gate configuration and lead to disordered N-termini to form a partially open gate.

Interestingly, only in C3, corresponding to the completely open gate, the tail of Rpt6 was stabilized and resolved in the $\alpha 2$ - $\alpha 3$ pocket (Figure 6C). In the meantime, the $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$, and $\alpha 4$ subunits showed additional motion shifting away from the central pore (up to 2.9 Å for $\alpha 4$) from C2 to C3 to further open the gate in C3, resulting in the absence of their N-termini from the gate region (Figure 6E). Our results suggest that the insertion of the Rpt6 C-terminus into the $\alpha 2$ - $\alpha 3$ pocket may trigger relocations of the consecutive $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 3$, and $\alpha 4$ subunits, and consequently a complete opening of the CP gate.

Discussion

Ever since the discovery of the multi-component “Ub-dependent ATP-dependent protease” in the mid 1980ies (Ganoth et al., 1988; Hershko et al., 1984; Hough et al., 1986), the quest to identify the Ub-binding subunit has been on. Over the years, three proteasome subunits situated in the RP, Rpn10, Rpn13 and Rpn1, have been found to associate with Ub, and crosslinking has verified their capacity to bind polyUb in 26S holoenzymes (Chojnacki et al., 2017; Husnjak et al., 2008; Shi et al., 2016; van Nocker et al., 1996a; van Nocker et al., 1996b). However, their relationship one to another on the proteasome and their relative contributions to the catalytic efficiency of Ub-conjugate degradation remain to be elucidated. Recent advances in cryo-EM technology have revealed that 26S holoenzymes are not static but adopt a number of conformations correlated to distinct nucleotide states (Chen et al., 2016; Ding et al., 2017; Luan et al., 2016; Unverdorben et al., 2014; Wehmer et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2018). During these conformational changes, the Ub-binding subunits shift relative to each other, raising the possibility that polyUb chains are handed over from site to site

during the catalytic process, and finally handed over to proteasome-associated DUBs for release (Chojnacki et al., 2017). Due to the dynamic nature of this process and of the proteasome itself, capturing polyUb on proteasome has been extremely challenging, and to date, no proteasome structure has resolved the molecular location of non-covalently attached polyUb.

We carried out cryo-EM analysis of the 26S proteasome in the presence of K48-Ub₄ and ATP, and revealed an ensemble of proteasome structures with distinct conformations, with three of them (C1-a, C1-b, and C2) resolved at near atomic resolution. Our structural, biochemical and biophysical analyses confirmed the presence of K48-Ub₄ and the induced conformational changes. The major structural findings are: (1) the newly identified C1-b state shows a downward position of the lid and a stable conformation of Rpn1 in comparison to the Ub-free “resting state” C1-a, indicating the influence of K48-Ub₄ to proteasome at the initial steps of the degradation process, and (2) an extra density connected to Rpn1 in the C3-b map attributed to the bound K48-Ub₄. This is the first time that tetraUb has been localized in an intact 26S holoenzyme. The completely open CP gate and fully aligned translocation channel suggest that C3-b is activated for substrate proteolysis.

Based on our ensemble of proteasome maps, we propose a sequence of events induced by engagement of K48-Ub₄. Upon accepting K48-Ub₄, the lid tilts downward toward Rpn1 creating a more steady conformation C1-b, as Ub-accepted state (Figure 7 Step 1). This movement brings the peripheral Ub-receptors (Rpn10, Rpn13) closer to the Ub/UBL-binding platform in the base, Rpn1. Next, a dramatic rotation of the lid triggered by tetraUb aligns the ATPase ring quite well with the entrance of CP in C2, forming a contiguous translocation channel, as Ub-engaged state (Figure 7 Step 2). This lid movement correlates with a partially open gate possibly transduced through the Rpn6- α 2 interaction. Only upon formation of a contiguous channel in C3-a, engagement of the unstructured tail of substrate by the ATPase pore would be “translocation competent”. The large conformational change of the ATPase ring may facilitate the insertion of the Rpt6 C-terminus into the α 2- α 3 pocket, leading to a

completely open CP gate (Figure 7 Step 3). Concomitantly, the wobble-like motion of the ATPase ring undergoing the ATP hydrolysis cycle drives the substrate through the channel (Sauer and Baker, 2011). Since C3-b is the only map in which the K48-Ub₄ density was resolved to attach to Rpn1, it likely represents the state in which the tetraUb chain is captured and stabilized by Rpn1, either before substrate engagement or just after having been released from the substrate (Figure 7 Step 4). In either scenario, this complex is ready to pass the substrate through the translocation channel into the proteolytic core for further substrate processing. In a recently resolved substrate-engaged proteasome, obtained at higher resolution, only the proximal Ub was visualised near Rpn10, with its tail interacting with Rpn11 (de la Pena et al., 2018; Dong et al., 2018). As such, in our case C3-b might represent a rate-limiting state, which is sufficiently stable allowing us to resolve the tetraUb-bound proteasome conformation.

Regarding gate opening, our current reconstruction of C3 at 6.8 Å resolution reveals four Rpt tail-insertions (Rpt2, Rpt3, Rpt5 and Rpt6), although we note that recent higher resolution cryo-EM maps of 26S proteasome in the open gate states reveal five tail-insertions (the above four, along with Rpt1) (de la Pena et al., 2018; Dong et al., 2018; Eisele et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2018). Our ensemble of proteasome structures in the presence of K48-Ub₄ enabled us to propose a long-range regulation of gating, involving the propagation of the tetraUb-induced motion of the lid to the gate through the Rpn6- α 2 interaction, as well as ATP-hydrolysis coupled Rpt tail-insertion, and ultimately to gate opening.

Ideally with a polyUb-conjugate, shaving of the signal by Rpn11 should be timed after substrate is committed for degradation so as to ensure complete degradation of the current substrate. An unanchored Ub-chain, as used in the current study, would ultimately need to be released for proteasome (and Ub) recycling. At our cryo-EM condition, affinity of proteasome for free Ub chain is not saturating (Figure S5A), and the majority of proteasome particles are not expected to be found stably associated with Ub₄, yet transient on/off interactions apparently affect proteasome conformations

(for instance in C1-b). Putting together, the above reasons explain the challenges to capture tetraUb on proteasome and the paucity of resolved Ub-bound C3-b conformation. The cohabitation of K48-Ub₄, Rad23, and USP14/Ubp6 on Rpn1 (Figure S5E) provides a platform for polyUb chain trimming to accelerate Ub recycling. The need to accommodate K48-Ub₄ and USP14/Ubp6 simultaneously might be an explanation for the novel position of tetraUb on Rpn1 that differs from published reports focused on mono- or diUb (Chojnacki et al., 2017; Shi et al., 2016).

To summarize, our study added several new conformational states to the proteasome functional cycle that may correlate to the proteasomal intermediate states whose formations were induced by K48-Ub₄. Categorizing each state according to the alignment of ATPase ring and CP gate, relative positions of pore loops, and CP gate opening status, we propose a sequence of events driven by K48-Ub₄ and nucleotide. For the first time, a proteasome structure is resolved with K48-Ub₄, which localized on the Rpn1 PC-crown of C3-b, notable as it is compatible for simultaneous binding of Ubp6 and Rad23 to Rpn1. Our results provide new insights into the structural mechanism of proteasome allosteric coordination induced by tetraUb and take a step forward towards elucidating the structural mechanism of substrate delivery and processing by the proteasome.

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Author contributions

Z.D., Y.C., and M.H.G. conceived and designed the experiments. Z.D., Z.F., Y.W., and I.S. purified proteins. Z.D., I.S., Z.F., and Y.W. performed functional analysis. M.H. and C.W. performed MS analysis. Z.D., Z.F., C.X., and Y.W. performed data collection. Z.D. and C.X. reconstructed the structures. Z.D., C.X., and Y.C. analyzed the structures. Z.D., Y.C., M.H.G., C.X., and I.S. wrote the manuscript.

Author declarations

During the reviewing process of this manuscript, three cryo-EM studies on 26S proteasome structures were published, in which conformers with open gate of the CP and engaged substrates were presented (de la Pena et al., 2018; Dong et al., 2018; Eisele et al., 2018).

Accession numbers

Cryo-EM maps have been deposited in the EMDB under accession codes *****. Pseudo-atomic models for *** have been deposited in the PDB under accession numbers of *****, respectively.

Declaration of Interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Figure 1. Cryo-EM maps of the functional states of yeast 26S proteasome in the presence of K48-Ub₄ and ATP. (A–E) The cryo-EM maps of proteasome corresponding to (A) C1-a, (B) C1-b, (C) C2, (D) C3-a, and (E) C3-b states. Each state was shown in two different side views (the second one clockwise-rotated 90° relative to the first one). The lid was colored in dodger blue, the ATPase ring in medium purple, CP in grey, and the rest in green. See also Figure S1-S4 and Table S1.

Figure 2. A comparison of conformations between C1-a and C1-b. (A) Atomic models of C1-a and C1-b, colored according to the B-factor distribution. B-factors were calculated to range from 60 Å² (blue) to 340 Å² (red). Subunits showing relative high B-factor values in C1-a were labeled. (B) Conformational variations between C1-a (grey) and C1-b (blue) of selected subunits, with the rotation angle and shift distance being labeled. See also Figure S3-S4 and Movie 1.

Figure 3. Distinct location of the extra density connected to Rpn1 resolved in our C3-b map. (A) The location of additional density connected to Rpn1 resolved in our C3-b map. This extra density (transparent red) increasing the size of Rpn1 (medium purple). (B) Association of 26S proteasome and K48-Ub₄ monitored by a gel-shift assay. K48-Ub₄ could retard migration of proteasomes, whereas monoUb failed to do so even at a 4-fold molecular excess over tetraUb. To provide biochemical evidence

for tetraUb binding to proteasome, we increased the molar ratio of tetraUb up to ~700-fold excess to proteasome for a detectable shift by native gel. **(C)** The density corresponding to K48-Ub₄ (PDB 2O6V, low-pass filtered, red) can be accommodated into the extra density (transparent red). **(D)** Location validation of tetraUb by reference-free 2D analysis of the nanogold-labeled tetraUb-bound proteasome data. Showing is the diagram of the nanogold labeling assay, and a reference-free 2D class average of the NS-EM data, in the similar viewing angle as in **(A)**. The substantially dark density corresponding to nanogold (indicated by a blue arrow) is located in the entrance of RP mouth near Rpn1. **(E)** Rpn1 model structure from C3-b, with N-term in blue, PC domain in green, and C-term in red. Schematic representation of Rpn1 domain used in the study (PC-I domain in green and PC-II domain in grey). **(F)** Gel shift assay showed that Rpn1 PC domain alone was competent to completely strip tetraUb from proteasome; while Rpn1^{PC-I} or Rpn10^{UIM} were less efficient at out-competing tetraUb prebound to 26S proteasome. See also Figure S5 and Table S2-S4.

Figure 4. Conformational changes of the proteasome lid upon RP activation. (A) Lid conformational comparisons among various states. The maps were aligned by their CPs, and the lid of the different states were found to show quite different rotational orientations, as denoted by the arrows in red. In the second panel, $\alpha 2$ subunit from CP and the interaction anchor point between $\alpha 2$ and Rpn6 are indicated by black arrows. **(B)** Variations of the distance between the tips of Rpn5 and Rpn6. Distance (in Å) between L27 in Rpn5 (cyan) and M1 in Rpn6 (red) was shown for each state. See also Movie 1 and 2.

Figure 5. Pore loop configuration in the ATPase ring of proteasome in distinct states. (A-C) Left: cutaway side views of the ATPase ring (shown in model) of (A) C1-b, (B) C3-a, and (C) C3-b, with the pore loops denoted by thick red loops. Right: The individual ATPase subunits (shown in map) visualized in the same orientation. The red dot represents the position of the conserved tyrosine residue of the pore loop. The height of the pore loop was denoted by the dashed black line. See also Figure S6-S7.

Figure 6. Gate-opening mechanism of the CP. (A) Top view of the CP in C1, with the resolved inserted C-termini of Rpt2, Rpt3, and Rpt5 (red density), showing a closed-gate configuration. The rendering style was followed throughout. (B) Top view of the CP in C2 with the inserted C-termini of Rpt2, Rpt3, and Rpt5, showing a partially-open-gate configuration. (C) Top view of the CP in C3 with the inserted C-termini of Rpt2, Rpt3, Rpt5, and Rpt6, showing a fully-open-gate configuration. (D) Superimposed CP structures of C1 and C2, with an enlarged view on the right. The black arrows indicate the expanding direction of helix 0 (indicated by black dashed boxes). The distance variations are listed in a table below. (E) Superimposed CP structures of C2 and C3. The rendering style is as in (D). See also Figure S8-S9.

Figure 7. Proposed mechanistic model induced by engagement of K48-Ub₄. In the resting state C1-a, the intrinsic dynamic nature of the Ub-related subunits may facilitate the recruitment of polyUb or Ub-conjugated proteins. Upon accepting K48-Ub₄, the lid tilts downward toward Rpn1 creating a more steady conformation C1-b, as Ub-accepted state (Step 1). Next, a dramatic rotation of the lid triggered by Ub aligns the ATPase ring with the entrance of CP in C2, forming a contiguous translocation channel, as Ub-engaged state (Step 2). This lid movement correlates with a partially open gate possibly transduced through the Rpn6- α 2 interaction. Only upon formation of a contiguous channel in C3-a, engagement of the unstructured tail of substrate by the ATPase pore would be “translocation competent”. The large conformational change of the ATPase ring triggered by ATP hydrolysis (indicated by white star) may facilitate the insertion of the Rpt6 C-terminus (indicated by yellow rectangle) into the α 2- α 3 pocket, leading to a completely open CP gate (Step 3). The K48-Ub₄ chain is captured and stabilized by Rpn1 in C3-b (Step 4). Then this complex is ready to pass the substrate through the translocation channel into the proteolytic core for further substrate processing.

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